

LIGHT ABSORPTION OF NICKEL ACETATE AND NICKEL PERCHLORATE

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Light absorption of nickel acetate and nickel perchlorate in aqueous solutions has been studied spectrophotometrically in the visible region between 430 m μ and 760 m μ at different concentrations. In the case of nickel acetate, the molecular extinction coefficient curve shows continuous absorption in the violet region and a maximum absorption in the red at about 715 m μ . Dilution of the solution results in an increase in the molecular extinction coefficient at all wave-lengths, but this increase is more marked in the region of maximum absorption at the red end than in the region of continuous absorption at the violet end. The effect of dilution has been explained. In the case of nickel perchlorate, the general form of the absorption curve remains the same as with nickel acetate, but there is a distinct shifting of the band maximum towards shorter wave-lengths on dilution. The comparison of the two salts brings out the influence exerted by the anions on light absorption.

Several workers have studied the light absorption of nickel salts. Much of the early work, however, was of a qualitative nature. Hartley (*Sci. Trans. Roy. Soc. Dublin*, 1900, 7, 253) studied the absorption spectra of coloured salts including those of nickel with special reference to the effect of dilution and rise of temperature on light absorption. The change of absorption on dilution of saturated solutions of deliquescent salts was attributed to the formation of molecules of more complex hydrated compounds. Müller (*Ann. Physik*, 1903, *iv*, 12, 767; 1906, *iv*, 21, 515), as a result of quantitative work in this field, observed that there was uniformity in the absorption of nickel salts in dilute aqueous solutions but the concentrated solutions had different tints and the colour of those salt solutions for which Beer's law was fulfilled within the limits of the visible spectrum was found to be independent of the temperature. Houston and co-workers (*Proc. Roy. Soc. Edin.*, 1913, 38, 137, 156); studied the light absorption of nickel salts in aqueous and non-aqueous solutions in the visible and ultra-violet light. They found that the absorption was much greater in the case of non-aqueous solutions such as those in acetone or alcohol. Houston and Cochrane (*ibid.*, 1913, 33, 147) obtained absorption curves for nickel sulphate and nickel acetate in the visible region and observed that the two curves are similar but the absorption of nickel acetate was slightly greater than nickel sulphate throughout the visible. Datta and Deb (*Phil. Mag.*, 1934, *vii*, 20, 21) studied the absorption spectra of paramagnetic halides of the iron group, (including that of nickel chloride), and their solutions at different temperatures in water, ethyl alcohol and concentrated hydrochloric acid. Kahanowicz (*Z. Physik*, 1931, 68, 126) obtained the extinction coefficients for infinitely dilute electrolytic solutions containing nickel and other metals throughout the visible spectrum. Von Koczkis (*Z. Physik*, 1930, 89, 274) found that Lambert-Beer law holds for nickel chloride.

The present investigation was undertaken to make a study of the effect of dilution on the light absorption of nickel salts. The nickel salts selected for the present study were nickel acetate and nickel perchlorate on which little work of a quantitative and systematic nature has so far been done.

EXPERIMENTAL

In all the experiments mentioned below nickel acetate and nickel perchlorate of high purity, prepared according to the methods described, were made use of and solutions of different

concentrations were prepared in conductivity water. The extinction coefficients were measured with a Hilger Nutting spectrophotometer.

Preparation of Nickel Acetate.—Chemically pure acetic acid supplied by Merck was used in the preparation of nickel acetate. Pure basic nickel carbonate (Merck) was dissolved in slight excess of acetic acid. The solution was heated on a water-bath and small quantities of nickel carbonate were added gradually until no more of CO_2 was evolved. The excess of carbonate was removed by filtration and the filtrate left at room temperature to undergo slow evaporation. In a fortnight's time beautiful green crystals of nickel acetate separated out. The crystals were washed with water and recrystallised to obtain a pure sample of the salt. The pure salt on analysis closely corresponded to the formula $\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Preparation of Nickel Perchlorate.—Pure basic nickel carbonate supplied by Merck was dissolved in a solution of pure perchloric acid and the mixture heated on a water-bath, until the reaction was complete. The excess of basic nickel carbonate was removed by filtration and the filtrate heated to 110° to expel excess of the acid. The solution was kept in vacuum over calcium chloride for several days for crystallisation. After a week's time, the salt separated out in long green needles. The crystals are highly hygroscopic and soluble in water, in alcohol and acetone. The salt was recrystallised twice to get a pure sample. The analysis of the salt showed that its composition corresponded to the formula $\text{Ni}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The melting point of the salt was found to be 200° corresponding to that obtained by Benrath, Hontung and Wilden (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1930, **143**, 298).

Absorption Spectra.—Nickel acetate solutions of $M/4$, $M/16$ and $M/32$ strengths were prepared in conductivity water, and immediately after the preparation of each solution its light absorption was measured in the visible region by means of Hilger-Nutting spectrophotometer. Care was taken to screen the tube from light during two successive readings. The temperature of the solution was nearly 30° . The results which represent the mean of several readings are represented in Fig. 1.

In the case of nickel perchlorate, solutions of the same strengths were employed. The rest of the procedure was also the same as in the case of nickel acetate. The extinction coefficients at various wave-lengths are recorded graphically in Fig. 2.

For comparison, the extinction coefficient curves of nickel acetate and nickel perchlorate are drawn in Fig. 3. A 2 cm. tube was used for measurement of extinction coefficients throughout.

FIG. 2

Nickel perchlorate soln.

DISCUSSION

From Fig. 1, it is seen that nickel acetate shows continuous absorption in the violet region and a maximum absorption in the red at about $715 \text{ m}\mu$. Dilution of the solution results in an increase in the molecular extinction coefficient at all wave-lengths, but this increase is more marked in the region of maximum absorption at the red end than in the region of continuous absorption at the violet end. There is no appreciable change in the position of the band. The effect of dilution on the extinction coefficient may be explained in more than one way. One possible reason for this effect may be the gradual elimination of the influence exerted by the negative ions on the absorption of the nickel ion due to dilution. The other and more probable reason is the progressive hydration of nickel ion brought about by dilution, resulting in an orientation of an increasingly larger number of water molecules round the ion, previous to the actual formation of nickel hydroxide.

In the case of nickel perchlorate, there is a continuous absorption at the violet end and a maximum absorption in the red region of the visible spectrum at about $715 \text{ m}\mu$ with $M/4$ solution (Fig. 2). In this case, also, dilution causes an increase in the extinction coefficient throughout the range of the visible spectrum, although this increase is more marked in the region of the maximum absorption than in the region of continuous absorption at the violet end. With nickel perchlorate, however, there is a distinct shifting of the band maximum towards shorter wave-length on dilution, which indicates a change in the nature of the absorbing entity. Nickel perchlorate, being a highly hygroscopic substance, will form a number of complex hydrated compounds on dilution, which may lead to a slight change in the quality and quantity of absorption. Apart from this, nickel ions in a solution of nickel perchlorate may also undergo progressive hydration on dilution as mentioned above in the case of nickel acetate.

FIG. 3

Absorption curves of nickel acetate and perchlorate

The absorption curves for nickel perchlorate show a remarkable similarity to those for nickel acetate (Fig. 3), particularly at higher concentrations. The points of maximum absorption in both cases lie at about 715 $m\mu$ at $M/4$ dilution. However, at $M/16$ and $M/32$ dilutions, the points of maximum absorption for nickel perchlorate shift gradually towards the shorter wave-lengths, while the points of maximum absorption for nickel acetate remain stationary. This shows that the negative ion exerts no appreciable influence on the absorption of the nickel ion at higher concentration, but it does exert some sort of influence on the absorption of nickel ions at high dilutions.

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